

THE INFLUENCE OF *CELEBRITY ENDORSE, WORD OF MOUTH AND BRAND IMAGE* ON INTEREST IN BUYING CIMORY YOGURT ON THE TIKTOK APPLICATION IN BANDUNG

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of celebrity endors, word of mouh and brand image on interest in buying cimory yogurt on the tiktok application in Bandung at PT Cisarua Mountain Dairy Tbk. This study uses quantitative descriptive method, the population in this study is the community in Bandung. Determination of population and sample using the cochar formula so that it gets a total of 385 respondents, research data is analyzed using descriptive analysis, and verifiative analysis and data analysis techniques using statistical applications in the form of SPSS 25. The results of the descriptive analysis showed that the variables celebrity endors, word of mouth, brand image and buying interest had a very high average value. Furthermore, the study had a significant influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable, significant values for the variables celebrity endors, word of mouth, brand image and buying interest were 0.01 and 0.00 respectively so that < 0.05 means (H1) (H2) and (H3) accepted, with the conclusion of celebrity endors, word of mouh and brand image Has a significant influence on the interest in buying cimory yogurt partially. Then the simultaneous significant test (F test) was $0.00 < 0.05$ meaning (H4) was accepted, with celebrity endors, word of mouh and brand image having a significant influence on interest in buying cimory yogurt simultaneously.

Keywords: Celebrity Endors, Word of Mouth, Brand Image and Buying Interest.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Since the pandemic hit, a healthy lifestyle has become an option, by managing a healthy lifestyle, it will be stronger to face the virus. Various ways are done to meet this lifestyle, ranging from exercising to consuming healthy foods including through milk. According to the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) in 2019, Indonesia's milk consumption was 16.23 liters / capita / year. This number has increased from the previous year of 0.20 liters / capita / year. The amount of milk consumption of Indonesian people is low compared to countries in Southeast Asia. Brunei consumes 129.1 liters/capita/year, Malaysia 50.9 liters/capita/year, Singapore 46.1 liters/capita/year and Vietnam 20.1 liters/capita/year (Anggraeni et al., 2021).

Table 1: Tingkat Production Susu in Indonesia 2018-2022

No	Year	Ton
1	2018	951 003,95
2	2019	944 537,08
3	2020	946 912,81
4	2021	946 388,17
5	2022	968 980,14

Source: BPS (Central Bureau of Statistics)

It can be seen that milk production in Indonesia has fluctuated due to public awareness of a healthy lifestyle since the pandemic has resulted in increased milk production.

Probiotic drinks containing *Lactobacillus* are growing rapidly due to their health benefits. The effect of daily consumption of probiotics in fermented milk on the gizi status of school children for 37 days was shown to improve nutritional status both anthropometrically and biochemical parameters. The lifestyle of people who are aware of health causes yogurt functional food products to be in demand in the community, especially among adults to children. (Novitasari et al., 2022).

According to the Top Brand Index of yogurt rating data in Indonesia for 2019-2023, Cimory is in the top position, below there is Brand Activa, then Freshtime, ducthmill and elle & vire, but for five years The Cimory brand has decreased in 2022-2023 from 67.40 to 63.20. This fact can be said that cimory yogurt has not been able to dominate market share and has an impact on sales levels so that it is suspected that there is a change in consumer behavior towards buying cimory yogurt products.

PT Cisarua Mountain Dairy (Cimory) is a manufacturer of protein-based packaged food and beverages. One of the popular products they market is cimory yogurt. (Irianto et al., 2022).

The ease of making yogurt has given rise to many new players at the level of home industries or MSMEs that are more innovative and cannot be ignored, several yogurt brands in Bandung (local) namely KPBS, Freshtime, Odise yoghurt, Bandung yoghurt, Youjel, Lmilk yoghurt and Jaya yoghurt (Hasibuan, 2021).

The rapid development of technology affects the marketing era, Marketing using traditional media shifts to digital media or better known as digital marketing (Indri ferdiani suarna et.al, 2022) As of January 2019, as many as 93% of internet users in Indonesia search for goods or services online, 90% of users visit online stores with various devices, 86% of users make online transactions from various devices (laptops and mobile), 37% of users make transactions through PCs or laptops, and 76% of users make online transactions through smartphone devices. From the explanation above, it implies that the potential of online shopping is quite developed in Indonesia, which must be balanced with digital marketing by business actors (Utami & Marzuko, 2021). Social media can encourage interpersonal communication Utilizing web-based technology, social media transforms communication into participatory conversations (Indri Ferdiani, 2022).

Some of the social media used, namely Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Line, and Whatsapp (Manik Pratiwi, 2020) and Tik Tok are one of the most popular platforms today. Tik Tok provides a means of sharing content that is very varied in terms of creativity, video challenges, lipsync, songs, dancing, singing and others, TikTok provides opportunities as a means of promotion (Dewa & Safitri, 2021).

Brand Ambassador according to Lea-Greenwood is a brand representative who affirms the brand with its reputation, exerts a significant impact on customer perception of the brand and organization or the tools used by companies to communicate and connect with the public, about how they increase sales in (Siskhawati & Maulana, 2021). *Brand ambassadors* consist of advertising content that highlights the celebrity's face, affects the memory of consumers. A celebrity is someone who is famous, popular, has a certain personality, and has an inner reputation (Yanti & Gusfa, 2022). The selection of brand ambassadors is usually based on branding through a famous celebrity (Putra, 2020).

The dissemination of sales of a product through word of mouth can be trusted as a strategy that quickly disseminates information and is easily trusted by consumers (Febryanti & Hasan, 2022).

Until now, Instagram and Tik-Tok online promotion media are marketing strategies chosen by Cimory to market their products well in order to maintain people's buying interest during the pandemic to date (Febryanti & Hasan, 2022). Although interested by many consumers, some people think differently about Cimory Yogurt Squeeze, people consider that the packaging of Cimory Yogurt Squeeze is less attractive related to the design and color of the packaging, indicating that word of mouth has not been so effective because of the lack of consumer invitation to people (Eni, 2023), according to Sernovitz in (Fenanda, 2020) explained that the word of mouth means to give people a reason to talk about the product and make the conversation easier, This indicates that consumers are dissatisfied with the Cimory Squeeze product (Kusumah & Madiawati, 2022),

According to Tjiptono on (Ferdiana Fasha et al., 2022) Brand Image is about product descriptions and consumer trust in the brand or image of a product in the minds of consumers in a dominating manner, then consumers see the brand of the product that comes to mind. Many consumers are less interested in Cimory products, this can be seen from consumer statements in general they are less interested in finding information about

Cimory products, Cimory products are less known by the public and in terms of benefits, resulting in many people who are not interested / interested in Cimory products. (Nurhidayah, 2020). Based on the above, research was conducted on people in Bandung who had bought Youghurt Cimory products. This research was conducted on various considerations so that it indirectly affects behavior patterns in everyday life, so the author conducted a study entitled "**THE INFLUENCE OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT, WORD OF MOUTH, AND BRAND IMAGE ON INTEREST IN BUYING CIMORY YOGURT ON THE TIKTOK APPLICATION IN BANDUNG**"

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Marketing is a marketing activity including branding using various web-based media, Digital marketing describes the management and implementation of marketing using electronic media as well as the application of digital technology that forms online channels (online channels) to the market (websites, e-mail, databases, digital TV and includes blogs, feeds, podcasts, and social networks that contribute to marketing activities that aim to get profit, (Arfan & Ali Hasan, 2022).

Social Media Marketing

Social Media Marketing is a marketing technique using social media facilities to promote products or services more specifically. A good content display can make online product or service website visitors interested in the products and services we display (Taan et al., 2021). In today's digital era, blogs, Wikipedia, and social networks are the most common forms of social media and are often used by humans in this world and social networks are the most popular medium in the social media category, examples of social media include Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, Line, Skype, Telegram, Instagram, Path, TikTok and others. (Divine & Social, 2022)

Celebrity Endors

Celebrity endorsement according to Shimp is a strategy to use artists as advertising stars in media ranging from print, social media, and television media (Muchsin Saggaff & Widiyanti, 2020), Shimp also said that five special attributes of celebrity endorsers with the acronym TEARS, consisting of *Trustworthiness*, *Expertise* which are two dimensions of *credibility*, *physical attractiveness*, *respect* and *similarity* (Purbohastuti & Hidayah, 2020). According to Kotler & Armstrong on (Ristauli Hutagaol & Safrin, 2022) *celebrity endorsement* is the use of sources as attractive or popular figures in advertising, so as to strengthen the image of a brand in the minds of customers.

Word of Mouth

Word of mouth is defined as an activity to provide information on the assessment or view of a product of goods and services, whether the product or service is suitable for consumption or not for potential consumers. (Umar Bakti et al., 2021), Word of Mouth is a marketing activity that triggers consumers to talk about, promote, recommend and sell the brand of a product to potential consumers (Nisa, 2022).

Brand Image

Brand Image is the perception and belief held by consumers, as reflected by associations embedded in customer memory, which are always remembered first when hearing slogans and embedded in the minds of consumers (Peronika et al., 2020). Brand image is the beliefs and perceptions of consumers about a particular product Lau & Phau in (Annissa & Paramita, 2021). According to Gross and Kitchen on (Yanti & Gusfa, 2022) Brand image is an overall picture of an object that is interpreted subjectively in the mind of a person or group.

Buying Interest

According to Kotler & Keller, Assael in (Andrew, 2019) Buying interest is part of the component of consumer behavior in consuming attitudes, the tendency of respondents to act before the purchase decision is actually implemented. According to Schiffman & Kanuk in (Maulana, 2022) Buying interest is something psychological strength that exists within an individual, which has an impact on an action.

Frame of Mind

Research Paradigm

Hypothesis

The hypothesis is as follows:

- H1: *Celebrity Endorse* has a significant and positive effect on consumer buying interest in Cimory yogurt in Bandung partially.
- H2: *Word of Mouth* has a significant and positive effect on consumers' buying interest in Cimory yogurt in Bandung partially.
- H3: *Brand Image* has a significant and positive effect on consumer buying interest in Cimory yogurt in Bandung partially.
- H4: *Celebrity Endorse*, *Word of Mouth* and *Brand Image* together have a significant and positive influence on the Interest in Buying Cimory yogurt in Bandung simultaneously.

RESEARCH METHODS

The quantitative approach is a research method in certain populations or samples, because the research data is in the form of numerical numbers so that data analysis uses statistics with the aim of testing the hypotheses that have been set (Sugiyono, 2022), in this research aims to test the influence of Celebrity Endorsement, word of Mouth and Brand Image on buying interest.

Data type

According to (Sugiyono, 2022) Data sources are divided into two parts, namely:

1. Primary data is data obtained through interviews or filling out questionnaires.
2. Secondary data i.e. researchers do not directly receive from the data source.

Population

The subjects who are the population in this study are consumers or people who buy Cimory yogurt in Bandung and use the Tiktok application activity, but in this case the population of cimori consumers of Tik Tok users is unknown.

Sample

According to (Sugiyono, 2022) samples are part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population, therefore, the calculation of the number of samples uses the Cochran formula (Sugiyono, 2022). Here is the calculation

$$n = \frac{z^2 \cdot p \cdot q}{e^2}$$

So

$$n = \frac{z^2 \cdot p \cdot q}{e^2} = \frac{(1,96^2) \cdot (0,5) \cdot (0,5)}{(0,5^2)} \frac{0,9604}{0,25} = 3.8416 \text{ (385 people)}$$

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

(Ghozali, 2018) states that the normality test is a test with the aim of testing whether in a regression model, confounding or residual variables have a normal distribution.

Multicholinerity Test

Multicollinearity was first introduced by Ragner Frisch, which is a very high linear relationship in regression models in each independent variable. Some explain that multicollinearity testing aims to test whether regression models are found to have correlations between independent variables (Azizah, 2021).

Heteroscedasticity Test

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in a regression model there is an inequality of variables from the residual of one observation to another.

Autocorrelation TEST

A good regression model is one that is free from autocorrelation. The measuring tool used to detect the presence of autocorrelation in this study uses the Durbin-Watson (DW) test, the following is a table for decision making on the presence or absence of autocorrelation according to (Ghozali, 2018).

Linierias Test

According to Ghozali (2022) "The linearity test is used to see whether the specifications of the model used are correct or not". Whether the functions used in an empirical study should be linear, quadratic or cubic.

ANALYSIS DESIGN AND HYPOTHESIS

Descriptive Analysis

According to (Sugiyono, 2022) descriptive analysis is an analysis carried out to determine the existence of independent variables, either only on one or more variables (stand-alone variables or independent variables) without making comparisons of the variables themselves and looking for relationships with other variables.

Verification Analysis

According to (Sugiyono, 2022) a verifiative research method is a research method that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables, or a method used to test the correctness of a hypothesis.

Hypothesis Test Design

Multiple Regression Analysis

The analysis used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis. According to (Ghozali, 2018) multiple linear regression analysis is an analysis used to determine the dependence between one dependent variable (bound) and one or more independent variables (free / explanatory). The regression model in this study is in the form of an equation with the following model:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

Partial Significant Test (T Test)

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the t test basically shows how far the influence of one independent variable individually in explaining the dependent variable.

Simultaneous Significant Test (Test F)

According to (Ghozali, 2018) "The F test basically shows whether all independent or independent variables included in the model have an influence together on the dependent variable".

Determinant Coefficient Test (R2)

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the coefficient of determination (R2) serves to see the extent to which the overall independent variable can explain the dependent variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Profile

Ket		Org	%
Gender	Male	152	39,7%
	Woman	233	61,55%
Age	17-22	186	48,3%
	23-28	115	29,6%
	29-34	19	4,9%
	>35	65	16,8%
Employment	Student / student	148	28,,3%
	Private employees	81	16,3%
	Businessman	67	15,3%
	Wiraswasa	50	9,3%
	Other	39	4,4%
Income	< 1,000,000	110	28,8%
	1.000.000-3.000.000	132	34,5%
	> 3,000,000	143	37,4%
Age of consumption	< 1 year	186	48,3%
	1 year	120	31,1%
	>2 years	79	20,5%
Purchase frequency	Every day	49	12,7%
	Once a week	152	39,4%
	Monthly	184	47,7%

Classical Assumption Test Results

Normality Test Results

Based on the results of the graph normality test, that points that spread around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line regression are feasible to analyze the variables celebrity endors (X1), word of mouth (X2), brand image (X3) and buying interest (Y). Thus the regression model satisfies the normality/normally distributed assumption.

Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.642	1.337		.480	.631		
	Celebrity endor (X1)	.235	.053	.189	4.403	.000	.308	3.250
	Word of mouth (X2)	.301	.044	.311	6.852	.000	.274	3.654
	Brand image (X3)	.635	.050	.466	12.781	.000	.424	2.360

a. Dependent Variable: Y

The result is that multicollinearity with tolerance results in the output of the *coefficient coefficient* table, each independent variable has a VIF value of < 0.10, which is the Celebrity Endors (X1) 0.308, Word of Mouth (X2) 0.274 and Brand Image (X3) 0.424 So it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity between variables.

While the *value of Variance Inflation Factor* (VIF) in the output results above that < 10 are variables Celebrity endors (X1) 3,250, Word of Mouth (X2) 3,654 and Brand Image (X3)

2,360. So it can be stated that the assumption in this model does not occur multicollinearity between variables.

Heteroscedasticity Test Results

The *scatterplots* chart shows that there is no clear pattern, and the points spread above and below the zero on the Y axis, it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur. So that regression models are feasible to use to predict the dependent variable Buying Interest (Y) based on the independent variables Celebrity endors (X1), Word of Mouth (X2), Brand image (X3).

Autocorrelation Test

Model Summary ^b					
Type	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.886 ^a	.785	.783	2.429	1.960
a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2					
b. Variable: Y					

Based on table 4.13 DW values of 1,960 > 1,842 (DW / du table) and smaller than 4 - du (DW table) which is 4 - 1,842 = 2,158 it can be concluded that the decision is accepted and no auto relation occurs.

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS RESULTS

Celebrity Endors

The overall Celebrity Endors (X1) variable is at a very high continuum level of 87.17%, in line with previous research stating that the celebrity endors variable affects buying interest to get the largest coefficient value (Ramlawati & Lusyana, 2020).

The highest value on the trustworthy dimension related to Celebrity Endors can be trusted in creating content about cimory products at 91.01%, in line with Arora in (Savitri, 2020) mentioning the use of celebrity endorsers will make trust significantly increase purchases. While the lowest value on the "trustworthy" dimension of the statement "Celebrity Endors

is consistent in making messages about cimory products" at 84.1%, in line with other studies stating that consistent endorsements give consumers a sense of confidence in buying products (Dzulhidayat, 2022).

Word of Moth

Intotal, all Word of Mouth (X2) variables are on a very high continuum of 84.53%, in line with previous research, stating that there is an influence of *word of mouth* on consumer buying interest (Image et al., 2023).

The highest value on the wom marketing dimension relates to being willing to explain good information about known cimory to friends or family by 87.11%, in line with previous research someone who likes to voice his opinion can influence respondents to visit Legipait Coffeeshop (Putri, 2020). While the value of the te indicator is low, in the dimension of "organic Word of Mouth" regarding the statement "I want to tell my experience because I like cimory products" by 83.53%, in line with previous research, it can be seen that there is still a low value in the statement "I like to tell pleasant experiences" (Balengka et al., 2021).

Brand Image

Basedon the analysis of the continuum line as a whole, the Brand Image variable (X3) is at a very high continuum level, amounting to 87.17%. in line with previous research Brand image has a significant influence on buying interest (Ali, 2020).

The highest statement on the image-forming dimension related to the brand and packaging of cimory yogurt and the catchphrase is easy to remember has a value of 91.01%, in line with previous research stating that the highest value in the question of respondents strongly agrees that the Garnier brand is easy to remember (Widyaningrum & Musadad, 2021) . While the low te value is found in the dimension of "Image Formation" regarding the statement "the price of cimory yogurt products is in accordance with product quality and affordable for me" with respondents' acquisition of 84.15%, In line with previous research stated that price perception increases, shopping habits will decrease, then the influence of price perception on shopping issignificant (Muna & Sulaiman, 2020).

Buying Interest

Based on the overall continuum line analysis, the Buying Interest (Y) variable is at a very high continuum level of 85.68%, in line with previous research it was concluded that buying interest confidence has a high effect (Hesti et al., 2023).

The highest statement on the transactional dimension of cimory yogurt attracts customer attention has a value of 88.93%, in line with previous research stating that Legipait Coffeeshop provides a place as comfortable as possible so that consumers will make purchases (Putri, 2020). While the indicator that received a low response on the "Transactional" dimension of the statement "Cimory yogurt is my first choice in buying yogurt products for consumption" obtained respondents by 84.93%, In line with previous

research, respondents will buy Kenangan Coffee as the first choice when they want to buy the lowest mean value drink (Priskila Angelin & Dwi Astono, 2022).

Verification Analysis Results

Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	0,642	1,337		0,480	0,631
Celebrity endors (X1)	0,235	0,053	0,189	4,403	0,000
Word of Mouth (X2)	0,301	0,044	0,311	6,852	0,000
Brand Image (X3)	0,635	0,050	0,466	12,781	0,000

From the regression equation above, the conclusion can be explained as follows:

1. Constant value of (Y) = 0.642

Based on the regression coefficient, it can be seen that a constant value of 0.642 means that if Celebrity Endors (X1), Word of Mouth (X2), and Brand Image (X3) are equal to 0, then the Buying Interest (Y) of cimory yogurt is 0.642

2. Celebrity Endors (X1) of= 0.235

The regression coefficient of the Celebrity Endors variable (X1) = 0.235 shows that for a positive value, every increase in Endorsement by 100 score units, then buying interest (Y) will increase by 23.5

3. Word of Mouth (X2) = 0.301

The regression coefficient of the Word of Mouth variable (X2) = 0.301 shows that for every positive increase in brand image by 100 units of score, it will be followed by an increase in buying interest (Y) of 30.1

4. Brand Image (X3) = 0.635

variable regression coefficient (X3) = 0.635 indicates that positive value, every increase in Brand Image by 100 units of score, will be followed by an increase in buying interest (Y) of 63.5. Inline with previous research, the Regression Coefficient of Brand Image, WoM, and Brand image have a positive and significant effect on buying interest (Rahma & Setiawan, 2021).

Artificial P Test Results (T Test)

Variabel	T Hitung	T table	Hasil
Celebrity Endors	4,403	1.966	Berpengaruh
Word of Mouth	6.852	1.966	Berpengaruh
Brand Image	12.781	1.966	Berpengaruh

Sumber: Data Primer Diolah (2023)

1. The Effect of Celebrity Endors (X1) on Buying Interest (Y)

The result of the Celebrity Endors variable hypothesis test showed t_{count} 4.403. With the number of samples (n) = 385 and $k = 3$, the table t value is 1.966. Based on the criteria, t is calculated greater than t in the table ($4.403 > 1.966$), using a significance level of sig value smaller than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$). Thus H_0 is rejected, but with the criterion H_1 is accepted. It is partially concluded that the Celebrity Endors variable has a significant effect on buying interest, in line with the results of research from (Wiwoho, 2023) the results of the t test of the significance level of the Celebrity Endorser variable of $0.01 < 0.05$ and the calculation results obtained a calculation number of $2.618 > t_{table}$ of 1.985 concluded that Celebrity Endorsers have a significant effect on Buying Interest.

2. Word of Mouth (X2) to Buying Interest (Y)

The result of the Word of Mouth variable hypothesis test shows t_{count} 6.852. With the number of samples (n) = 385 and $k = 3$, the table t value is 1.966. Based on the criteria, t is greater than t in the table ($6.852 > 1.966$), and in using significance levels where the sig value is smaller than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$). Thus H_0 is rejected, but with the criterion H_1 is accepted. It is partially concluded that the Word of mouth variable has a significant effect on buying interest, in line with the results of the study (Astuti et al., 2021) the results of the Word of Mouth variable t test produce a sig t value of 0.003 which means $0.003 < 0.05$ with a calculated t value of 3.042 greater than t table 1.98118. The value is that the Word of Mouth variable has a significant effect on Emina's Product Buying Interest.

3. The Effect of Brand Image (X3) on Buying Interest (Y)

The result of testing the Brand Image variable hypothesis shows t_{count} 12,781. With the number of samples (n) = 385 and $k = 3$, the table t value is 1.966. Based on the criteria, t is calculated greater than t in the table ($12,781 > 1.966$), and in using significance levels where the sig value is smaller than 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$). Thus H_0 is rejected, but with the criterion H_1 is accepted. It can be partially concluded that the Brand Image variable has a significant effect on buying interest, In line with the results of research from (Purwati & Cahyanti, 2022) the conclusion is that because of the $>$ value ($4.735 > 1.99773$), H_0 was rejected, meaning that brand image partially affects Buying Interest (Peronika et al., 2020).

Simultaneous Test (Test F)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8206.080	3	2735.360	463.534	.000 ^b
	Residual	2248.320	381	5.901		
	Total	10454.400	384			
a. Dependent Variable: Y						
b. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X1, X2						

It can be seen that the results of hypothesis testing show a *calculated F* value of 463,534. with the number of samples as much as (n) = 385 and k = 3 obtained DF of 2.63. Based on the criteria, *F* is *calculated* greater than *F*_{table} (463.534 > 2.63), and in using a level of significance where the sig value is smaller than 0.05 (0.00 < 0.05). Thus H₀ is rejected, as well as the criterion H₁ is accepted, it can be concluded that simultaneously the variables Celebrity Endors, Word of Mouth and Brand Image have a significant effect on Buying Interest.

The results of this study are in line with previous research which states that the F test result is smaller than < 0.05, so the regression model is fit or feasible to use because brand ambassadors, word of mouth (WOM), and brand image simultaneously affect buying interest. So F count is greater than F table (F count > F table, 16.571 > 2.699) the level of suitability of the research model with research data is good (Rahma & Setiawan, 2021).

Test Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Model Summary				
Type	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.886 ^a	0,785	0,783	2.42922

With formula $Kd = R2 \times 100\%$

Where:

Kd = Coefficient of determination

r² = Correlation coefficient

Then kd = 0.783 x 100%

$$= 78.3\%$$

The adjusted *R square* of 0.783 (78.3%) shows that the influence of Celebrity Endors, Wom and Brand Image has an effect on the interest in buying cimory yogurt combined by 78.3%, the remaining 22.7% is influenced by other variables that were not included in this study, inline with research stated that the test results were known that the value of R² =

59.6 percent, Buying interest in coffee free space coffee shops in Denpasar was influenced by the variables Celebrity endorser (X1), Brand image (X2), and Brand image (X3) and the remaining 40.4 percent was influenced by other variables that were not studied in the study (Kadek Riza Nevilia, 2023).

CONCLUSION

1. The results of the study on the distribution of respondents' assessments of the variables Celebrity Endors (X1), Word of Mouth (X2) and Brand Image (X3) on buying interest (Y) Yoghurt cimory in Bandung had an influence on the marketing strategy efforts carried out by PT Cisarua Mountain Dairy Tbk.
2. The results of the Significance Test (Test F) in this study show that the variables Celebrity Endorse (X1), Word of Mouth (X2) and Brand Image (X3) simultaneously affect Buying Interest (Y).
3. The results of the Significant Test (Test t) show that the Celebrity Endors variable (X1) has an effect on Buying Interest (Y) partially.
4. The results of the Significant Test (Test t) show that the Word of Mouth variable (X2) has an effect on Buying Interest (Y) partially.
5. The results of the Significant Test (Test t) show that the Brand Image variable (X3) has a partial effect on Buying Interest (Y).

Advice for Companies

1. Based on the recapitulation of the distribution of respondents' assessments of the Celebrity Endors (X1) variable, there are indicators of obtaining low responses, on the "trustworthy" dimension regarding the statement "Celebrity Endors is consistent in making messages about cimory products" with respondents gaining 84.1%, researchers advise companies to pay more attention to company managerial related to agreements made with other parties and be more thorough in controlling and evaluating as well as processes The selection of Celebrity endors must also be paid more attention to by asking for consumer opinions or using other recrutmen processes.
2. In the Word of Mouth (X2) variable, an indicator that received low responses on the dimension "organic Word of Mouth" statement "I want to tell my experience because I like cimory products" gained respondents by 83.5%, researchers suggest that companies make a marketing strategy directly with regard to consumers, by asking for feedback or testimonials, thiscan help determine the level of satisfaction by preparing a *form* custom or provide a product *rating* page.
3. In the Brand Image variable (X3), the lowest response indicator, in the dimension "Image Formation" statement "the price of cimory yogurt products is in accordance with product quality and affordable for me" respondents amounted to 84.1%, researchers suggested paying attention to selling prices to suit the market as well as encouraging the formation of product images at prices, with price perception strategies that tend to provide benefits for consumers.

4. In the Buying Interest variable (Y), there is an indicator that obtained the lowest response on the "Transactional" dimension of the statement "Cimory yogurt is my first choice in buying yogurt products for consumption" with respondents gaining 83.3%, researchers advise companies to determine specific patterns (market positioning) so that companies get consumers that are in accordance with the target market, with companies highlighting specialties that are not owned by competitors to customer

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Further research needs to explain more fully by adding to the latest book theories, expanding research so as to obtain more varied results by combining other studies so that the relationship between various variable that can measure consumer purchase minimum is known, pFurther research is expected to review more sources and references related to Cimory Yogurt so that the research results can be better and more comprehensiveip.

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